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Towards Linking Coseismic Slip to Interseismic Coupling at Cascadia

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Summary

The downdip limit of coseismic slip in Cascadia is a key source parameter for seismic hazard assessment because it influences predicted ground motions, tsunami excitation, and coastal land-level change from future great megathrust earthquakes. This parameter must be specified in the western United States earthquake hazard model, yet its value remains uncertain because it is inferred indirectly from present-day interseismic coupling models, paleoseismic estimates of coastal subsidence, and assumptions about the relationship between interseismic locking and coseismic rupture (Frankel et al., 2018; Petersen et al., 2020; Wirth & Frankel, 2019).

This project addresses one important source of uncertainty: whether coastal subsidence estimates from the 1700 Cascadia earthquake record only coseismic deformation, or whether they also include early postseismic deformation. Coastal subsidence from the 1700 event is commonly inferred from intertidal foraminifera preserved in salt-marsh stratigraphic sequences (Wang et al., 2013; Kemp et al., 2018; Padgett et al., 2021). These data have usually been interpreted as recording rapid coseismic subsidence. However, studies of foraminifera response times in coastal Oregon indicate that foraminifera may take approximately 11–25 months to recolonize following sudden inundation (Horton et al., 2017). This raises the possibility that the paleoseismic subsidence estimates include one to two years of early postseismic vertical motion following the earthquake.

We investigated this possibility by generating suites of Cascadia coseismic slip distributions and computing the associated early postseismic deformation due to stress-driven afterslip and viscous mantle flow. The goal is to determine how much postseismic deformation may contribute to the coastal vertical displacement field recorded by foraminifera, and how accounting for this contribution changes estimates of coseismic moment, magnitude, and the downdip extent of rupture.

Our main finding is that stress-driven afterslip generally contributes much less to the coastal vertical deformation field than coseismic slip. In contrast, viscous mantle flow can produce coastal vertical motions that are comparable in magnitude and spatial pattern to the coseismic deformation field. As a result, including early postseismic deformation tends to reduce the coseismic moment and magnitude required to fit the foraminifera-derived subsidence data. However, because the vertical deformation patterns and hinge-line locations associated with coseismic slip and viscous mantle flow are similar, including postseismic deformation does not shift the inferred downdip edge of coseismic slip as much as originally anticipated.

Motivation and Scientific Context

Two primary sources of information are commonly used to estimate the downdip extent of future Cascadia coseismic slip: present-day interseismic coupling models and paleoseismic estimates of slip or subsidence from past earthquakes. Both approaches contain important uncertainties.

Interseismic coupling models are inferred primarily from geodetic data. These models provide valuable information about where the megathrust is currently locked or creeping, but they provide only a snapshot of a time-dependent earthquake-cycle process. Coupling may evolve over decadal to centennial timescales, and present-day locking may not correspond directly to the eventual area of coseismic rupture (Mavrommatis et al., 2014; Mallick et al., 2021; Sherrill et al., 2024). In addition, offshore geodetic constraints remain sparse, and standard kinematic inversions have limited resolution of the downdip edge of coupling. These limitations make it difficult to infer the downdip rupture extent directly from present-day coupling alone.

Paleoseismic coastal subsidence estimates provide an independent constraint on the 1700 earthquake. The hinge line between coseismic uplift and subsidence is expected, from elastic dislocation theory, to occur near the downdip limit of coseismic slip. Thus, the pattern of coastal subsidence can help constrain whether coseismic rupture extended to near the coastline or remained farther offshore. Previous studies have used foraminifera-derived subsidence estimates to infer spatially variable rupture and slip during the 1700 event (Wang et al., 2013; Kemp et al., 2018). Other work has shown that deeper coseismic slip, including slip east of the coastline, can be consistent with coastal subsidence constraints under some source assumptions (Melgar et al., 2022).

The interpretation of these data depends on the timing of the biological response relative to the earthquake. If foraminifera recolonization occurs months to years after sudden subsidence, then the observed stratigraphic signal may represent coseismic deformation plus some amount of early postseismic deformation. This is important because postseismic deformation can be large in subduction zones. Observations following recent great earthquakes, including the 2010 Mentawai and 2011 Tohoku-oki earthquakes, show that early postseismic vertical motions can be a significant fraction of the coseismic signal and can vary in sign and magnitude along the coast (Feng et al., 2015; Ozawa et al., 2012). Therefore, understanding whether the 1700 Cascadia subsidence estimates include postseismic deformation is important for using these data to constrain the coseismic rupture area.

Project Objectives

The objective of this work is to quantify the possible contribution of early postseismic deformation to coastal subsidence following the 1700 Cascadia earthquake and to evaluate how that contribution affects estimates of coseismic slip and rupture extent. The project has three related goals.

First, we generate a broad suite of physically plausible coseismic slip distributions for the 1700 Cascadia earthquake. These realizations span a range of magnitudes, stress drops, and downdip

rupture limits. Rather than attempting to identify a single preferred slip model, we explore many candidate models that could plausibly represent the 1700 event.

Second, for each coseismic slip realization, we compute the early postseismic deformation over the time window relevant for foraminifera recolonization. The postseismic model includes both stress-driven afterslip on the megathrust and viscous flow in the mantle wedge and subducting mantle. Afterslip is computed from coseismic stress changes using a rate-strengthening friction law, following the stress-driven afterslip framework developed for coseismic and postseismic modeling by Fukuda and Johnson (2021). Viscous mantle flow is computed using pre-computed viscoelastic Green's functions.

Third, we compare the combined coseismic and postseismic vertical deformation fields with the foraminifera-derived coastal subsidence observations. This allows us to identify which coseismic slip models are consistent with the data when postseismic deformation is included and to compare those models with the slip distributions inferred when the subsidence is treated as purely coseismic.

Modeling Approach

The modeling framework begins with a set of static coseismic slip distributions on the Cascadia megathrust. The upper and lower limits of allowable slip are prescribed, and the downdip limit of rupture is varied across realizations. Earthquake magnitude and spatially heterogeneous stress drop are also varied in order to sample a broad range of plausible rupture scenarios. The intent is to explore the model space extensively, rather than to impose a narrow prior on the slip distribution.

Figure 1. An example of a coseismic slip realization and computed coseismic and postseismic deformation. From left to right: input coseismic slip, computed afterslip distribution, computed coseismic vertical motions (meters), computed mantle flow contribution to vertical displacement (meters), computed afterslip contribution to vertical displacement (meters), total computed vertical displacement (meters).

For each coseismic rupture realization, we compute postseismic deformation using a physically coupled afterslip and viscous relaxation model. Coseismic slip produces stress changes on the megathrust. These stress changes drive afterslip in velocity-strengthening regions of the fault, governed by a simple rate-strengthening friction law. The same coseismic slip distribution also drives viscoelastic mantle relaxation. The viscous flow component is computed using a Cascadia subduction-zone geometry with elastic overriding and downgoing plates embedded in viscous mantle regions. Figure 1 shows an example computation of vertical motions for an example input coseismic slip distribution.

In the current parameter exploration, coseismic slip distributions span moment magnitudes of approximately M_w 8.6–9.2. Afterslip is computed using a range of rate-strengthening parameters, and viscous mantle flow is evaluated for mantle viscosities spanning 10^{17} – 10^{18} Pa s. The total modeled vertical displacement at the coast is the sum of the coseismic displacement, early postseismic displacement due to afterslip, and early postseismic displacement due to viscous mantle flow. We evaluate this total displacement over an approximately 11–25 month postseismic window, corresponding to the estimated response time of foraminifera following sudden tidal inundation (Horton et al., 2017).

Results

The results show that the two postseismic mechanisms have different effects on the coastal vertical deformation field. Afterslip generally produces a vertical deformation contribution that is smaller than the coseismic signal. In many cases, the afterslip contribution is approximately an order of magnitude smaller than the coseismic contribution at the coast. Thus, afterslip alone does not substantially alter the interpretation of the foraminifera-derived subsidence data.

Figure 2. Seismic moment, M_o , and moment magnitude, M_w , for all coseismic realizations that fit the subsidence data. Far right, predicted motions at observation sites for all coseismic realizations (blue dots), and models that fit the data (red dots). White circles and diamonds are observations from Wang and Kemp studies.

Viscous mantle flow has a larger effect. For low transient mantle viscosities, early viscous relaxation can generate widespread coastal subsidence with amplitudes comparable to the

co-seismic subsidence. This means that a portion of the subsidence recorded by foraminifera could reflect deformation that occurred during the first one to two years after the earthquake, rather than during the earthquake itself. In the model suites that fit the subsidence data, the inclusion of viscous-flow-driven subsidence generally lowers the coseismic slip, moment, and magnitude required to match the observations.

This result has an important implication for estimates of the 1700 earthquake magnitude (Figure 2). If the observed coastal subsidence is interpreted as entirely coseismic, larger coseismic slip and larger moment are required. If some of the subsidence is instead produced by early postseismic viscous relaxation, then smaller coseismic moment can reproduce the same total subsidence. In the modeled cases, including postseismic deformation shifts the acceptable model population toward lower moment and lower magnitude relative to coseismic-only interpretations.

Figure 3. Contours of mean coseismic slip for (left) all realizations, (middle) realizations that fit the data but only using coseismic displacements, and (right) realizations that fit the data using computed coseismic and postseismic displacements. Note that the mean coseismic slip for models with postseismic deformation included is on average smaller than for all realizations and models with only coseismic displacements included.

The results also show that the effect on the downdip edge of coseismic slip is more subtle. We initially expected that adding postseismic deformation might strongly change the inferred downdip rupture limit, because the coastal hinge line is sensitive to the depth extent of slip. However, the modeled vertical deformation patterns from coseismic slip and viscous mantle flow are similar in many cases, including similar hinge-line locations (Figure 3). As a result, adding early postseismic deformation does not move the inferred downdip edge of coseismic slip as much as anticipated. The postseismic contribution affects the amplitude of coseismic slip and the inferred moment more strongly than it affects the downdip rupture location (Figure 3).

The comparison with interseismic coupling models remains important. Preliminary comparisons indicate that the coseismic slip distributions that fit the subsidence data commonly extend deeper

than the bottom edge of the present-day fully locked zone. This is consistent with the broader conceptual model that coseismic rupture may extend outside the region that is currently fully locked. In this view, the locked zone evolves throughout the interseismic period as creep fronts migrate into the region that ruptured in the previous earthquake. Present-day coupling may therefore represent a time-dependent stage in the earthquake cycle rather than a fixed map of future coseismic rupture (Bruhat & Segall, 2016; Sherrill et al., 2024).

Implications for Cascadia Hazard

These results are relevant to Cascadia seismic hazard in several ways. First, they show that paleoseismic coastal subsidence estimates should not automatically be interpreted as purely coseismic deformation. If foraminifera response times allow one to two years of postseismic deformation to be recorded, then early viscous relaxation may need to be included when using these data to constrain earthquake source models.

Second, the results suggest that estimates of the 1700 earthquake moment and magnitude may depend on whether postseismic deformation is included. Because viscous mantle flow can contribute significantly to coastal subsidence, coseismic-only models may overestimate the slip or moment needed to explain the observations. This does not mean that the 1700 event was necessarily small; rather, it indicates that the paleoseismic subsidence data alone may permit lower coseismic moment when early postseismic deformation is included.

Third, the results clarify which aspects of the source model are most affected. Early postseismic viscous flow appears to have a stronger influence on inferred coseismic moment and magnitude than on the location of the downdip rupture edge. This is encouraging for hazard applications because the downdip rupture limit remains a key parameter for ground-motion modeling. However, further work is needed to test the robustness of this conclusion across a wider range of mantle viscosities, fault friction parameters, slip distributions, and subduction-zone geometries.

Finally, the work helps link paleoseismic observations, interseismic coupling models, and earthquake-cycle physics. A central challenge in Cascadia hazard assessment is determining how present-day coupling relates to future rupture. This project contributes to that problem by combining coseismic slip models, early postseismic deformation models, and evolving interseismic locking models in a common earthquake-cycle framework. It also complements other approaches to Cascadia rupture modeling, including stochastic slip models and dynamic rupture simulations (Melgar et al., 2022; Ramos et al., 2021; Glehman & Gabriel, 2023).

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